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COLOR TRAITS AND FLORAL CHARACTERISTICS IN DIFFERENT GENOTYPIC GENERATIONS

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Аннотация: В настоящей статье представлен анализ равномерности окраски шерсти и направленности роста волос (или другого признака, связанного с "цветами") у ягнят голубой масти, полученных от скрещивания животных различных генотипов. Исследована корреляция данных признаков с равномерностью окраски шерсти, и на основе полученных результатов сформулированы выводы.

Ключевые слова: Голубые каракульские ягнята, селекция, скрещивание, направление роста волос (к головной части, к хвостовой части), смешанное, равномерность окраски шерсти (отличная, равномерная, неравномерная).

Abstract: This article investigates the color uniformity of blue offspring produced by matings of different genotypes, examines the orientation (open side) of the markings (gullar), analyzes the relationship between these traits and overall color uniformity, and presents conclusions.

Keywords: blue Karakul lambs; selection; mating; marking orientation-toward head; toward tail; mixed; color uniformity; excellent; uniform; uneven.

The Relevance of the Topic. Karakul sheep are currently bred in over forty countries worldwide. This has created significant opportunities for the widespread introduction of innovative technologies in developing effective breeding and genetic methods to manage their genetic potential and productivity, for expanding the breeding area for sheep with the most valuable colors and patterns, and for

simultaneously producing high-quality sheep. High-quality products contribute to ensuring food security for populations living in desert regions. Currently, extensive measures are being implemented to improve the Karakul breed by properly establishing Karakul sheep selection. As a result, based on the biological characteristics of the Karakul breed, increases in hide, wool, and meat productivity are being achieved. Scientific research in Karakul sheep breeding is being carried out in this direction.

In our Republic, Karakul sheep breeding is a vital sector of animal husbandry. This, in turn, allows for the rational utilization of desert and semi-desert regions and enables the production of unique Karakul pelt products with diverse colors and patterns. Furthermore, meat, milk, wool, and other products are also obtained. Therefore, expanding the breeding area of Karakul sheep, improving their genetic potential, and increasing their productivity are among the important scientific and practical tasks.

Research Objective. The objective of the study is to investigate the marking orientation of blue offspring obtained from matings of different genotypes, and the relationship of these indicators with color uniformity.

Research Location and Methods. The research was conducted on existing blue Karakul lambs of the South Uzbekistan breeding stock, under the conditions of the “Bobotog’ Suri Karakulchilik” LLC farm in Kumkurgan district, Surkhandarya region. In the experiment, studies were carried out to investigate the marking orientation of blue offspring obtained from matings of color-heterogeneous ♂ blue Afghan X ♀ black local (experimental) and ♂ blue South Uzbekistan X ♀ black local (control) groups, and the relationship of these indicators with color uniformity. The evaluation of the offspring was carried out based on the "Guidelines for breeding work in Karakul sheep breeding and evaluation (bonitification) of lambs" (2015) by S.Yu.Yusupov et al.

Color uniformity is among the paramount indicators in the selection process of blue Karakul sheep, holding critical importance in all situations. Even Karakul

pelts with high-quality curls (or markings) and wool fiber, and valuable coloration, are considered less valuable if their color is not uniform across the pelt surface. A lack of color uniformity leads to varied coloration and mottling/patchiness on the pelt surface, thereby reducing its quality.

A low score for this indicator (color uniformity) results in the wool fibers that form the curls having different lengths in various topographical sections of the pelt surface. This, in turn, increases the likelihood of different types of curls forming. Color uniformity is among the critically important indicators in the selection process of blue Karakul sheep, holding decisive significance in all situations. Even Karakul pelts with high-quality curls (markings) and wool fiber, possessing valuable coloration, are considered less valuable if their color is not uniform across the pelt surface. Lack of color uniformity leads to varied coloration and mottling on the pelt surface, thereby reducing its quality.

A low score for this indicator (color uniformity) means that the wool fibers forming the curls have different lengths in various topographical sections of the pelt surface, which in turn increases the likelihood of different types of curls forming.

Blue lambs with uniform color are also highly prized for breeding purposes. Therefore, the uniformity and clarity of their color are of high importance. Color uniformity is rarely observed in dark blue pelts. Primarily, medium blue pelts tend to be uniform. Considering the color of lambs is important in carrying out breeding work.

It is known that color uniformity is evaluated using three indicators: excellent, uniform, and uneven. Naturally, pelts rated as excellent and uniform are considered high-quality pelts.

The curls of blue pelts are larger, looser, and less tightly curled compared to those of black pelts. The darker the color of blue pelts, the more fully curled and robust their markings become. The reason for this is that white wool fibers are not as long as black wool fibers.

The differing lengths of wool fibers in various topographical parts of the pelt,

and the consequent formation of curls of different shapes, is considered one of the main factors affecting color uniformity. Furthermore, the presence of various types of curls on the pelt surface negatively affects the quality of the pelt and leads to a decrease in product quality.

Based on the aforementioned points, the results of the study on the color uniformity of blue Karakul lambs obtained during the research are presented in Table

Table 1

Degree of distribution of color uniformity in the obtained offspring, % ($\bar{X} \pm S_x$)

Groups	n	Color Plane		
		excellent	uniform	uneven
Experiment	297	48,5 \pm 2,9	37,7 \pm 2,8	13,8 \pm 2,0
Control	252	42,9 \pm 3,1	36,9 \pm 3,0	20,2 \pm 2,5

Analysis of the table data reveals that the experimental group demonstrated a superiority of 5,6% and 0,8% over the control group in terms of excellent and even color uniformity, respectively, among the presented indicators. Conversely, regarding the level of unevenness, the control group exhibited indicators 6,4% higher than those of the experimental group. It is noteworthy that in all instances, the experimental group lambs consistently showed superior performance in terms of color evenness compared to the control group lambs. Specifically, a higher prevalence of excellent and even color uniformity was observed. These findings are considered to be of significant importance in improving the hereditary traits of sheep and enhancing product quality.

The open side of curl patterns in generations and the correlation of these indicators with color uniformity. Karakul lamb pelts are categorized into several types based on the open side of their curl patterns. These include head-open, tail-open, and mixed appearances. Unique distinctions are observed in the variation of the open side of the patterns within each type of young lambskin. Our studies have shown that head-open patterns were most frequently found in lambs with semi-

circular pencil curls, while mixed and a small number of head-open patterns were observed in the elongated curl type. In lambs with rib-like and flat pencil curls, the presence of predominantly tail- and head-open patterns was determined.

Based on the above, the results of our study on the open side of curl patterns in blue Karakul lambs are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

**Open side of curl patterns on the skin surface of obtained generations, %
($X \pm S_x$)**

Groups	n	Open side of the curl patterns		
		Towards the head	Towards the tail	mixed
Experiment	297	46,1±2,9	34,0±2,7	19,9±2,3
Control	252	50,4±3,1	27,4±2,8	22,2±2,6

As we can see from the table data, focusing on the results obtained for head-open curl patterns, the offspring of the control group were 4,3 percent higher than the experimental group. In the case of tail-open curl patterns, the experimental group showed a 6,6 percent advantage over the control group. In the opening of mixed curl patterns, the control group recorded a 2,3 percent advantage over the experimental group.

In breeding work, the open side of curl patterns on the skin surface is primarily aimed at breeding offspring with head- and tail-open patterns. This is because beautiful patterns with high-quality characteristics are formed on the skin of such lambs. Our studies found a certain degree of correlation between the color uniformity of blue Karakul lambs and their curl characteristics, specifically the open side of the curl patterns. The results are presented in Table 3 below.

Table 3

Correlation of Color Uniformity of Obtained Generations with the Open Side of Curl Patterns, % ($X \pm S_x$)

Color	Experimental Group	Control Group
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Uniformity		Excellent n=144	Uniform n=112	Non-uniform n=41	Excellent n=108	Uniform n=93	Non-uniform n=51
Open Side of Curl Patterns	Towards the head	46,5±4,1	58,9±4,6	9,8±4,6	52,8±4,8	67,8±4,8	13,7±4,8
	Towards the tail	53,5±4,1	19,6±3,7	4,9±3,4	47,2±4,8	16,1±3,8	5,9±3,3
	Mixed	-	21,5±3,8	85,5±5,5	-	16,1±3,8	80,4±5,5

From the table data, we can see that in the correlation between color uniformity and the open side of the curl patterns. Among generations with excellent color uniformity, when curls opened towards the head, the experimental group showed a 6,3% lower value compared to the control group. When curls opened towards the tail, the experimental group was found to be 6,3% higher compared to the control group. In the case of mixed open curl patterns, no generations with non-uniform color uniformity were observed in either group.

In the case of uniform color uniformity. The experimental group's generations showed an 8,9% lower value compared to the control group for curls opening towards the head. For curls opening towards the tail, the experimental group was found to be 3,5% superior compared to the control group. In the case of mixed open curl patterns, the experimental group was also noted to be 5,4% superior compared to the control group.

In the case of non-uniform color uniformity, the experimental group's generations showed a 4,1% lower value compared to the control group for curls opening towards the head. For curls opening towards the tail, the experimental group was found to be 1% lower compared to the control group. In the case of mixed open curl patterns, the experimental group was noted to be 5,1% higher compared to the control group.

From the obtained data, we can conclude that in generations obtained from different genotypic pairings, the experimental group showed a 6,4% superiority in terms of excellent and uniform color uniformity compared to the control group.

If we pay attention to the results obtained regarding curls opening towards the head, the control group's generations were 4,3% higher than the experimental group. In the case of curls opening towards the tail, the experimental group had a 6,6% superiority compared to the control group. In the case of mixed curl patterns, the control group was noted to be 2,3% superior to the experimental group.

Accordingly, in the conditions of the experimental farm and other farms specializing in blue color, the use of rams of Afghan genotype (experimental group) is considered effective, and breeding the obtained offspring for pedigree purposes is deemed appropriate. Therefore, it allows us to conclude that these situations should be taken into account during the selection process.

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